

FIGHTING AI-DRIVEN CYBERCRIME IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

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Abstract

The paper explores the complexities of attribution and accountability in AI-enabled cybercrimes, focusing on cases when AI technologies are used for illegal activities like hacking, identity theft, cyber fraud, cyber terrorism, prevention or limitation of access to public computer networks, cyberbullying, hate speech, or malware distribution. The primary research questions include: Which forms of cybercrime are dominant and, as far as possible, use artificial intelligence? How can the legal system attribute liability in cases of AI-driven cybercrime? What role do AI developers play in preventing the misuse of their technologies? And can AI systems themselves be considered autonomous actors, thus complicating accountability? To address these questions, the paper will present case studies of AI-driven cybercrime incidents and how they can be treated in Serbia's legal system. A comparative analysis will be employed to examine how different international frameworks approach liability for AI-related offenses and how they can be used to improve legal treatment of this type of cybercrime in the Republic of Serbia. The crucial aim is to identify key patterns in liability attribution, with an emphasis on the responsibilities of different stakeholders, as well as to provide insights into the challenges of processing AI-driven cybercrime. The conclusions will offer practical recommendations for how legal systems should handle the increasing use of AI in cybercrime, contributing to the development of more robust cyber laws and AI ethics regulations.

Keywords: *cybercrime, artificial intelligence, AI-driven crime, regulation, liability*

1 INTRODUCTION

The expansion of information-communication technologies and the integration of artificial intelligence into everyday life have significantly transformed the nature of cyber threats. While AI-driven tools can enhance cybersecurity defences, they also empower offenders to design and execute sophisticated attacks with minimal human intervention.

From automated malware generation to deepfake-based frauds, AI has redefined the boundaries between traditional and emerging forms of cybercrime.

Cybercrime, often referred to as computer crime, internet crime, digital crime, or high-tech crime, represents one of the fastest-growing areas of transnational criminal activity (Drakulić & Drakulić, 2014). The Republic of Serbia, aligned with international standards such as the *Budapest Convention on Cybercrime* (2001), legally defines and prosecutes these offenses under the term high-tech crime. According to the Serbian Ministry of Interior and the National CERT, the number and complexity of cyber incidents have increased dramatically in recent years, correlating with the global surge in AI utilization. This crime, like the COVID pandemic, covers vast areas and affects various and numerous victims. Thus, in China alone, almost every second computer is infected and the infection rate is 47%, with a tendency for widespread vulnerability in individual and business systems (Deepstrike, 2025). It is estimated that global cybercrime costs will reach 14 trillion USD by 2028, while average data breach expenses in 2025 already exceed 4.88 million USD, a 10% annual increase (VikingCloud Team, 2025).

The concern is fully justified if one takes into account the use of AI in the darknet, or dark web. They are increasingly using AI to reach their victims more easily, to better conceal their activities and, above all, to make detection of their 'deeds' more difficult. There are increasingly frequent and alarming warnings that AI is increasingly strengthening the dark web ecosystem (Telefonica Teh, 2025). Although it occupies only 0.1% of the Internet, this space records according to Pangarkar (2025) huge daily traffic. As of March 2025, over 3 million visitors access dark web platforms daily, with illegal websites accounting for about 60% of all domains; it is estimated to generate enormous illegal income about 1.5 billion dollars annual income from the sale of stolen data, counterfeit goods and other illegal products; rise in credentials - stolen credentials for accounts available on the dark web grew 82% in 2022, reaching an estimated 15 billion credentials - a major enabler of subsequent cyber-attacks. Bitcoin is the most used cryptocurrency on the dark web, accounting for over 98% of transactions; it is estimated that the number of active hidden services on the dark web is around 30,000. The USA is the country with the largest number of users of this web, followed by Germany, France and the United Kingdom. In such conditions, the application of AI is justifiably scary, as shown by the fact that in just one year, sales of AI-based tools (Wang, Arief & Castro, 2025) on the dark web have increased by over 200%, especially frequent identity theft scams that have quadrupled, and 73% of companies worldwide have experienced some form of AI-related data compromise (Telefonica Teh, 2025). Also, artificial intelligence is increasingly used as a response to various systems, especially government and business, in managing the risks of cyber-attacks or as support for security "patches", but also forensic techniques and tools (Vaadata, 2024).

The emergence of AI as both an instrument and a target of cybercrime adds unprecedented complexity to legal and forensic frameworks. Unlike conventional software tools, AI systems possess varying degrees of autonomy and learning capabilities. This is precisely why attributing responsibility to either human operators, programmers, or the AI system itself poses a profound legal and ethical dilemma. These challenges are especially pressing in jurisdictions such as Serbia, where rapid technological adoption coincides with evolving but still maturing cyber-legal structures.

This paper aims to analyse: (1) the role that AI developers play in preventing misuse (AI-driven cybercrime in Serbian practice) (2) the establishment of the capacity to respond to AI-driven cyber incidents (combating AI-driven cybercrime, possible or not?),

and (3) the ways in which liability can be attributed under current Serbian law (regulation as a presumption for the success of the fight against cybercrime in the Republic of Serbia). The structure follows a logical progression: conceptual definitions, legal frameworks, typology of AI-enabled crimes, national case studies, and policy recommendations.

2 AI-DRIVEN CYBERCRIME IN SERBIAN PRACTICE

The emergence of artificial intelligence as a tool for cybercriminal activities has significantly altered the landscape of digital threats in Serbia. Although there is still no official statistical category of “AI-driven crime,” several documented incidents and patterns confirm the presence of such phenomena. These crimes primarily include AI-assisted phishing and smishing, AI-based malware and ransomware, deepfake frauds, voice cloning (vishing), and automated hacking attempts.

Serbia’s National CERT and Ministry of Interior have repeatedly warned about phishing and fraud campaigns written in grammatically correct Serbian language, suggesting the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT, FraudGPT, or WormGPT for automated message creation. Similar to global trends, these AI systems can generate deceptive, credible messages mimicking official institutions or well-known brands (Naveed, et al., 2025).

Between 2023 and 2025, Serbia experienced multiple large-scale phishing campaigns targeting users of Telecom Serbia, Netflix, and the Serbian Treasury Administration (CERT, 2025). The sophistication of these campaigns, reflected in language fluency and personalized targeting, strongly suggests AI involvement.

In the Telecom Serbia campaign, users received fraudulent SMS messages inviting them to claim loyalty points by logging into a fake domain (MTS, 2025). Once credentials were entered, attackers withdrew funds from victims’ accounts. Similarly, the Netflix campaign used authentic logos and style to obtain payment information, while the Treasury Administration campaign distributed malware disguised as government notifications.

Voice phishing (vishing) campaigns have also emerged in Serbia, where attackers use AI voice cloning to impersonate officials or company representatives. According to the Ministry of Interior, citizens received calls from spoofed numbers where cloned voices urged them to “**verify bank information.**” Research by Azzuni & Saddik (2025) indicates that as little as 30 seconds of recorded speech is sufficient for realistic voice replication.

The most alarming case of AI-driven cybercrime globally – and one serving as a reference for Serbian analysis – occurred in 2024, when the British engineering company Arup lost \$25 million in a deepfake video scam (Magramo K., 2025). Deepfake frauds use AI algorithms to synthetically create realistic yet false video or audio material, often for extortion, political manipulation, or financial deception (Abbas & Taeihagh, 2024).

In Serbia, similar attempts have been detected through fake Facebook investment ads falsely attributing interviews to high-ranking officials, including the current Prime Minister. These deep fake campaigns used authentic visual and linguistic cues to persuade citizens to invest in fraudulent platforms. Though under investigation, they are presumed to have been developed with **GAN (Generative Adversarial Network)** technology.

AI has also revolutionized malware creation. Tools such as **WormGPT** and **FraudGPT** can autonomously generate malicious code, select attack vectors, and adapt to defensive systems in real time (Falade, 2023). According to RATEL and the National CERT (2020–2024), incidents involving unauthorized data collection, malware installation, and phishing remain dominant in Serbia. A steady annual increase demonstrates the growing sophistication of attacks, partly driven by AI technologies.

The use of AI in cybercrime challenges traditional criminal law doctrines. When AI systems autonomously generate malicious code or execute decisions, establishing *mens rea* and *causality* becomes difficult. Moreover, the ethical responsibility of AI developers is a growing concern, particularly when tools are designed without ethical constraints (e.g., WormGPT). Serbian legal scholars advocate introducing provisions for developer liability and mandatory ethical AI certification.

The Republic of Serbia has made notable progress in establishing a structured and comprehensive framework for combating cybercrime, including offenses potentially involving artificial intelligence. Through the adoption of specialized legislation, ratification of international conventions, and creation of institutional mechanisms, Serbia has positioned itself among the regional leaders in addressing high-tech and AI-related offenses. However, the dynamic evolution of AI technologies poses challenges that exceed the scope of existing regulatory mechanisms.

The integration of AI into cybercrime introduces numerous procedural and evidentiary difficulties:

- a) **Attribution and evidence collection:** AI-generated content (text, video, audio) often lacks unique digital fingerprints, complicating proof of authorship.
- b) **Cross-border complexity:** AI-driven attacks frequently rely on distributed cloud infrastructures located in multiple jurisdictions, necessitating international cooperation under the Budapest Convention and its additional protocols.
- c) **Forensic limitations:** Existing digital forensic tools are insufficient for analysing machine learning models or identifying algorithmic decision-making paths.
- d) **Lack of expertise:** Despite ongoing training programs, there remains a shortage of AI-savvy investigators and forensic experts capable of interpreting algorithmic behaviour.

Serbia's *Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence 2025–2030* emphasizes the importance of AI safety, ethics, and responsible innovation. It advocates the creation of a National AI Ethics Committee and proposes guidelines for AI accountability. In parallel, *The Strategy for Combating High-Tech Crime 2019–2023*, currently undergoing revision, is expected to integrate new measures specific to AI-driven threats, including:

- **Development** of AI-assisted forensic tools;
- **Introduction** of algorithmic liability provisions;
- **Enhanced** cooperation between academia, law enforcement, and the private sector;
- **Continuous** capacity building through education and international partnerships.

Despite these initiatives, the absence of explicit provisions on AI criminal liability remains a critical gap. Current interpretations rely on extending traditional criminal law principles (intent, negligence, causation) to AI-mediated scenarios, but such analogies are often insufficient when AI systems act autonomously or unpredictably.

In the European Union, instruments such as the AI Act (European Parliament and of the Council, 2024) and the Digital Services Act (European Commission, 2023) introduce obligations on transparency, explainability, and accountability for high-risk AI systems. Serbia, though not yet an EU member, follows these developments closely and aims to align its domestic legislation accordingly. The ongoing adoption of these norms represents both a challenge and an opportunity to modernize Serbian criminal law and cyber governance frameworks.

3 COMBATING AI-DRIVEN CYBERCRIME, POSSIBLE OR NOT?

It is, although it is often with little success and weak effects. Previous practice has shown great complexity and countless attempts. What is certain is that the fight against AI-driven cybercrime can be diverse, which depends on the criteria for classifying methods, techniques, measures, mechanisms and tools. Given the complexity and scope of this crime, the fight must be well-planned, long-term, comprehensive, systemic and systematic. Thus, based on the mechanisms of struggle, it can be: social, political, legal-ethical, criminalistics, organizational, procedural, technical-technological and/or educational. If the way of working is taken as a criterion, the fight can be individual and/or team. According to the length of action: short-term, medium-term and/or long-term, and according to the method of action: spontaneous or organized. The selected mechanisms can be undertaken preventively or subsequently, while according to the time of intervention they can be primary, secondary and tertiary. In any case, it is necessary to remove or mitigate the consequences that affect individuals, groups or en masse, and the measures taken will be individual, group or en masse. It would be optimal for the fight to be unified in such a way as to suppress the causes and remove the consequences. And, of course, enable the recovery of the attacked system.

Back in 2012, the American Standards Institute published a special guideline for computer security (NIST, 2012), revised it several times. It specifically stated that "effectively responding to incidents is a complex undertaking, establishing a successful incident response capacity that requires significant planning and resources". Establishing the capacity to respond (organization, society, government, etc.) to incidents is related to computer/cyber security, and it is the efficient and effective resolution of incidents. Achieving these requirements is made possible by a timely and high-quality incident response plan, which is implemented in at least four phases and requires the selection and complete preparation of the teams that will implement it, as well as the selection of appropriate tools and resources. Broadly speaking, the response plan must encompass and elaborate various forms of combat, synchronizing and harmonizing them with each other. It is important that all phases are included, that is, that each of them is well organized, managed and realized. The stages are: **preparation; detection and analysis; suppression and eradication; and recovery.**

In order for the response plan to be successful, not only preparation, detection and analysis are important, but also its extremely good knowledge, on the one hand, and for suppression, eradication and then recovery of the system, timely and effective identification of the response, on the other. All the more so because it, like any other phenomenon, has its own **life cycle**. Studying the life cycle is extremely important for understanding its essence and deciding what forms of struggle should be undertaken. Often the struggle is focused on eliminating the consequences instead of identifying the causes, methods, techniques and tools that have been applied. Such an approach makes it difficult to see the characteristics of the perpetrators and victims of this crime, as well as avoiding the interpretation of the space in which it takes place.

The new generation of cybercriminals, subtle and secretive, not only requires a new approach to cyber security, but also imposes the need to treat a new type of cyber threat differently due to the possibility of using AI. They simultaneously change the *modus operandi*, as well as give a new dimension to the life cycle of this crime. The life cycle of AI-driven cybercrime itself includes (Paloalto, 2023; Vidal E. R., 2025; GeeksforGeeks, 2025):

1. **examination**/reconnaissance;
2. **planning**/"arming";
3. **delivery**/transition from preparation to action;
4. **attack**/implementation and use/exploitation/transition from potential threat to actual intrusion;
5. **installation**/validation/verification of fulfilment of set goals, effects/establishment of permanent presence within the compromised system;
6. **command and control**/adjust external communication channel to send instructions, receive stolen data and operate in a compromised environment with full control;
7. **effect** on the goal.

Each stage of the life cycle carries specificities and special modalities. They need to be looked at and analysed in order for the cyber security response to be appropriate and effective. Therefore, the *modus operandi*, AI must be investigated. The *modus operandi* of AI-driven cybercrime is increasingly linked to organized crime and indicates that increasing the efficiency of criminal operations requires increasing their speed, reach and sophistication. Perpetrators, actors, threats use criminal and social criminal networks as tools for disruption (The SHERLOC, 2022; Wall D, 2017).

In order to determine the *modus operandi* of the perpetrators of this crime, their approach and forms of behaviour are analysed, that is, how and whether: a) preparation was undertaken; b) which methods were chosen for the execution of the crime, c) how many perpetrators there were, that is, suspects; and d) where they "operated".

- a) In the analysis of AI-supported cybercrime, unlike any other crime, it is determined how and which software and hardware was chosen to carry out the act. It is also part of a **serious and serious preparation** in order to find out whether these are premeditated acts and/or organized by several persons. It is increasingly evident that perpetrators of cybercrime prepare extensively and systematically, as well as investigators. The preparation consists of: choosing the victim; obtaining electronic addresses and other data related to the victim; collecting data on system weaknesses; locating materials, documents, data that you want to access; digging through the deepnet and the darknet to find the best tools and methods of execution, the nodes of the criminal network; choosing the way to destroy evidence; choice of ways of concealing and covering identity; choice of partners (accomplices). The choice of the victim, or goal depends on the motivation of the offender and the degree of vulnerability of the system. The existence of a large number of victims, of different profiles, is connected to this crime. The most effective way is vulnerability scanning because everyone (state, organization, group, individual) presents their services to the public, and they could be a channel for an attack. Frank Smith and Graham Ingram (2017) warn that threats to individuals are growing "almost exponentially" and that "government has lost the battle".
- b) Perpetrators of cybercrime **use special methods, tools, skills, and knowledge** to commit crimes (Drakulić & Drakulić, 2014) and are constantly improving. One of

these new methods/tools is deep fake (AI is behind the rise of deep fake and enables hyper-realistic fake audio or video recordings that can fool almost anyone) (Vazdar, 2025). Methods undergo numerous modifications, becoming more complex and sophisticated. Studying the methodology of committing the crime is doubly important: **for perpetrators profiling** (United States Government, 2024) and **victim profiling** (Havers, Tripathi, Burton, McManus, & Cooper, 2024). Changes and modifications in the characteristics of the victims are especially present, but two are particularly significant - age and number. The number of older people is increasing, with the fact that they are less likely to report "cybercrime to the police, bank or other authorities", but that is why, according to the FBI (2024) "people over the age of 60 report the highest losses from various forms of cybercrime, which is almost 5 billion dollars out of a total of 16 billion dollars lost in 2024." The mass of victims is an increasingly frequent feature of this crime (e.g. 353,027,892 victims in 2023, and the majority of incidents resulted from cyber-attacks) (Fox, 2024), especially since as a rule these crimes are concurring and affect a large number of victims. Also, victims from areas that were previously avoided for ethical reasons, such as health, are mentally ill persons (Monteith, Glenn, Geddes, Achtyes, Whybrow, & Bauer, 2024). The most vivid statement is for this second category: "The use of artificial intelligence to deceive individuals is of particular importance to psychiatry, because mental illness can increase vulnerability to cybercrime. Factors that can increase vulnerability to online deception include severe mental illness, emotional instability, poorer short-term memory, cognitive impairment, and lack of technical skills. In addition, impulsivity and overconfidence in information technology knowledge and skills can increase susceptibility to cybercrime. Psychiatrists should be aware that artificial intelligence is increasing the quantity and quality of cybercrime against individuals and to be able to recommend reliable sources of cyber security education to their patients..."

- c) The **number of perpetrators** (and associates/accomplices) and suspects is a characteristic of this crime. The most dangerous and attractive category are organized criminal groups. They are particularly related to AI-generated phishing, AI-driven malware and ransomware, AI-driven social engineering attacks, AI-based cyber espionage (Shoeb Ali Syed, 2022), AI cryptocrimes, but also certain acts of child abuse (Wang, 2020), thus the Internet Watch Foundation, IWF, identified a significant and growing threat of using AI for the production of child sexual abuse material, noting that "an initial report in October 2023 revealed the presence of over 20,000 AI-generated images on a dark web forum in one month, with more than 3,000 depicting criminal child sexual abuse activity. Since then, the problem has worsened and continues to evolve". Further, they warn that the reports from April 2023 to March 2024 (IWF, 2024), "contain a total of 375 reports that contained AI-generated content and child-assisted child abuse, peaking at 60 reports in February 2024". Many of these acts are the result of the "work" of criminal groups (e.g. members of "Scattered Spider" started the breach with a ten-minute vishing attack (voice phishing) posing as an employee in a phone call to the IT department asking for help and access to data). In a Trend Micro (2024) survey of cybercrime group categories, a distinction is made between: **small groups** with 1-5 members and revenues of less than \$500,000 per year (e.g. Scan4You); **medium groups** of 6-49 members, with annual revenues up to 50 million dollars (e.g. MaxiDed); and **large groups** with more than 50 members, and earnings over 50 million dollars per year

(e.g. Conti). The problem, of course, is the analysis of their structure and activities because they are anonymous, "invisible" and inaccessible, well hidden in the dark net. In any case, the activities of cyber groups are extremely present and often supported by national governments (primarily for intelligence and espionage purposes, as was the case with the North Korean group Lazarus). Governments themselves support organized cyber criminal groups through direct sponsorship, indirect support (hiding perpetrators) and/or through defensive cyber warfare (developing sophisticated cyber operations to protect their own networks and systems from attack) (UNODOC, 2020).

- d) The **location/scene of the crime** (Saqib, Faheem, India, Nituja, & India, 2025) is the fourth essential component of the modus operandi. The analysis of the crime scene of this form of cybercrime indicates its specificity, as well as a different approach to hiding evidence and the identity of the perpetrator. This analysis enables investigators to establish timelines of events, identify patterns, and overcome the challenges of adapting to the growing complexity and volume of data. The emergence of artificial intelligence technologies is transforming the processing of evidence, on the one hand, improving efficiency, precision and scalability, and the complex concealment of evidence and perpetrators, on the other. "*AI is also being used to reconstruct crime scenes through sophisticated 3D modelling techniques, which provide investigators with a detailed perspective of events and enhance courtroom presentations.*" In any case, AI is changing almost the entire picture of crime and forensic tools, especially cyber forensics, for detection, monitoring, analysis and presentation, as well as locating crime scenes. The changes are broad, deep, all-encompassing and in some ways terrifying. That is why specific experts are necessary whose knowledge can ensure the identification of the crime scene, the tools used, as well as the identification of the victims and the perpetrator (FBI, 2025).

4 REGULATION AS A PRESUMPTION FOR THE SUCCESS OF THE FIGHT AGAINST CYBERCRIME IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

In the process of the ratification of *The Convention on Cybercrime* (Budapest Convention, 2001) and additional protocols (*Law on the Ratification of the Additional Protocol to the Convention*, 2009, and *Law on Ratification of the Second Additional Protocol to the Convention on Cybercrime on Enhanced Cooperation and Discovery of Electronic Evidence*, 2022), the legislator in the Republic of Serbia decided to use term **high-tech crime** (hi-tech crime) for the crimes that are happening in the cyberspace. This led to introduction of criminal acts **against security of computer data** (Arts. 298–304a), **sexual offenses** committed through computer networks (Arts. 185, 185b); as well as criminal acts **against intellectual property** (Arts. 198–202) into Criminal Code of the Republic of Serbia but also gives possibility to process other criminal acts (such as crime against property, against economy, against legal instruments, against public peace, against constitutional order and security) under the jurisdiction of the Prosecutor for High-Tech Crime.

Each of these areas can be directly influenced by the use of AI. For instance, Articles 298–304a criminalize unauthorized access to protected computers, networks and digital data processing, computer data and programs destruction, computer sabotage, computer fraud, development and introduction of malicious software (viruses), as well as prevention and limitation of access to a public network, unauthorized use of a computer or

networks, etc. Sexual offenses such as the production or distribution of child pornography (Art. 185) and the abuse of communication technologies to target minors (Art. 185b) are increasingly linked to AI-generated deepfake materials. Furthermore, the use of copyrighted or patented works for AI training without authorization may violate Articles 199–202 concerning intellectual property.

It is expected that these three groups of criminal offenses could be directly influenced by mass usage of AI in the crimes, thus these ones will be further explored in the context of AI driven cyber-attacks that are currently happening in the Republic of Serbia, as well as potential usage of AI to conduct them if they are not detected in the wild. Furthermore, Serbia in 2023 adopted the *Law on the Organization and Competence of State Bodies for the Fight against High-Tech Crime*, which regulates the formation, organization, jurisdiction and powers of special organizational units of state bodies for the purpose of detection, prosecution and trial for criminal offenses determined as hi-tech crime.

Institutionally, Serbia has established a strong organizational framework for addressing cybercrime:

- The **Special Prosecutor’s Office for High-Tech Crime**, responsible for prosecuting all cases falling under the defined categories (with possibility that other criminal acts that potentially fall under jurisdiction could be influenced by AI);
- The **Department for the Fight against High-Tech Crime** within the Ministry of Interior;
- The **National CERT** (Computer Emergency Response Team), part of the **Regulatory Agency for Electronic Communications and Postal Services** (RATEL); and
- The **Information Security Inspectorate**, responsible for oversight of critical ICT systems.

The Statistical Bulletin of the Special Prosecutor’s Office for High-Tech Crime (2024) indicates a 10.31% increase in registered cases between 2023 and 2024, reaching a total of 7,198 cases, of which 3,888 involved unknown perpetrators. These data highlight both the rise of digital threats and the complexity of identifying offenders operating in or through AI-assisted mechanisms. Additional data show that 93 indictments and 8 full indictments were filed in 2024, with 39 plea agreements concluded. Although AI-specific cases are not yet statistically isolated, prosecutors report a growing number of offenses involving AI-generated phishing, voice cloning, and AI-assisted fraud (Vrhovno javno tužilaštvo, 2025).

Despite the extensive legal framework, AI-driven cybercrime presents unique challenges to regulation and enforcement. Traditional provisions are built on the assumption of direct human agency, while AI-enabled attacks often involve systems capable of self-learning, decision-making, and autonomous adaptation. This raises several legal questions:

- **Attribution:** Who is responsible—the user, the developer, or the AI system itself?
- **Mens rea:** Can intent be established when an AI independently adapts or modifies its actions?
- **Jurisdiction:** How to prosecute transnational AI attacks executed through cloud-based infrastructures?

While Serbian law currently lacks explicit norms addressing these specific dilemmas, the *Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence 2025–2030* outlines the need for a coordinated response integrating technological, organizational, legal, and ethical

safeguards. Future legislative amendments are expected to incorporate provisions on algorithmic accountability, data transparency, and explainability.

5 CONCLUSION – WHAT’S NEXT?

The continuous advancement of artificial intelligence technologies has transformed both the scale and sophistication of cybercrime, presenting unprecedented challenges for legal systems worldwide. The Republic of Serbia, while maintaining a robust institutional and legislative foundation, must now adapt its criminal law and cybersecurity frameworks to reflect the autonomous and adaptive nature of AI-driven threats.

This research identified that AI influences nearly every domain of cybercrime – from data manipulation and fraud to sexual exploitation and intellectual property violations. Serbian criminal law currently provides mechanisms to prosecute most of these offenses under existing provisions (Arts. 298–304a of the Criminal Code), yet the rise of autonomous AI systems calls for a more nuanced legal understanding of intent and liability.

Three critical conclusions emerge from the analysis:

1. **Legal adaptation is essential.** The Serbian criminal justice system needs to expand definitions of digital offenses to explicitly include AI-assisted and AI-generated cybercrimes. Concepts such as algorithmic accountability, explainability, and developer liability must be integrated into statutory law.
2. **Institutional and technical capacity must evolve.** Specialized training for prosecutors, judges, and forensic experts in AI technologies is necessary. The introduction of AI-powered forensic tools capable of analysing machine learning models, recognizing synthetic media, and identifying behavioural anomalies will enhance investigative efficiency.
3. **Ethical and preventive frameworks must accompany enforcement.** As AI technologies continue to develop, their misuse can only be mitigated through ethical governance, transparency obligations for AI developers, and cross-sectoral cooperation. Establishing an independent *AI Ethics Council* and implementing risk-based certification systems could help ensure the responsible use of AI across industries.

Looking forward, Serbia’s position as a regional leader in cybersecurity gives it an opportunity to shape normative standards that balance technological progress with human rights and rule of law. Future legislation should focus on proactive prevention, international cooperation, and education, ensuring that the benefits of AI outweigh its potential for misuse.

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